

THE MANIFESTATION OF VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL SYMBOLIC MEANS IN THE SYSTEM OF CULTURAL CONSTANTS "SUPERIOR - INFERIOR"

Kulpeisova T.,

Associate Professor

of Karaganda Technical University named after Abylkas Saginov

Nasyrova A.

Associate Professor

of Karaganda Technical University named after Abylkas Saginov

Abstract

The article deals with symbolic signs, which, being instruments of social regulation, use the language according to the social position of the communicant. These symbols of power and subordination in society contribute to the consolidation of the dichotomy "superior" - "lower" in the performance of the function of regulating social relations and the function of social orientation.

Keywords: hierarchical relations, socially oriented function, speech behavior, superior, inferior, social status, verbal symbolic signs, non-verbal symbolic signs.

Service relations are characterized by a pronounced hierarchy. The expression in speech behavior of the hierarchy of service relations depends primarily on the type of communication, on the degree of officiality. The more formal the relationship, the more signs of subordination in speech. Team members - employees of the same department - are usually "their own". Here, in non-strictly official and semi-official situations of official communication, the boss and subordinates can behave calmly, at ease, especially if they are of the same age and are on good terms. . When communicating with employees of other departments whom employees do not know very well, the interlocutors already control their behavior, even if they are equal in status. And of course, strict control of verbal behavior is present in an official conversation with a communicant whose position on the career ladder is much higher than the official status of the interlocutor. An attempt to determine the essence of the phenomenon of "social status" was made by Folomeeva T.V. and Fedotova S.V. During the experiment, they were divided into several groups. Within the framework of the first, social status is considered as a person's position in society. Similar data were obtained within the framework of the collected social representations, the core of which contained precisely these two concepts - "position" and "society". The second group of definitions reveals social status as a phenomenon that is constructed and chosen by the person himself, the individual can correct it. As part of the third group, it was indicated that social status is a characteristic that is assessed by members of society and affects how an individual is perceived, how they are treated, as well as the choice of a strategy of behavior in interaction with him [1, 7].

In any social action of people, T. Shibutani emphasizes, "the roles are in a mandatory relationship with each other, as in a drama, any role makes sense only when it is associated with the behavior of other actors" [2].

According to Z.A. Badretdinov power appears not as an imposition of one's plans, but as a process of possessing the very fact of this coercion, as a phenomenon that is significant for us [3]. By virtue of this understanding, it is necessary to approach power not through

the motive "why" we impose the will, but based on the principle "because" [4].

In particular, a successful attempt to analyze the relationship between superiors and inferiors was made by I.I. Dubinin in the dissertation on the topic "Methods of Expressing Hierarchical Relations in Organizational Communication". Focusing on the opposition "boss - subordinate" and putting forward the mutual influence of the parties on the success of hierarchical communication as one of the important factors, the researcher comes to the conclusion that at the verbal level it is realized in the features of the types of speech acts, referring to various speech genres, in a mismatch in "methods of influence and characteristics of the mode of expression" [5, 3], in operating with etiquette norms, in the pragmatic specifics of the language units used. According to I.I. Dubinina, building hierarchical relations with subordinates by the boss is based on the strategy of "official self-positioning and official distancing" [5, 3]. Maintaining them at the proper level is ensured by the strategy of "veiling", which implies the preference for indirect means of communication in order to "save face" of the boss (the author includes in the list of means of communication "euphemisms, indirect speech acts, hypothetical, impersonal and passive constructions, evasive answers, indefinite personal pronouns" [5, 13]). The use by the boss of other strategies - "discredit and job expansion" [5, 3] - on the contrary, causes damage to hierarchical relations. Behavioral characteristics of participants in hierarchical official business communication are also considered by the author in non-verbal terms. At the same time, the linguist sees the essential "temporal and spatial conditions of the communicative process, artifacts used by the subjects of the organization, kinetic, prosodic and proxemic components that perform the function of establishing, maintaining or breaking hierarchical relations" [5, 4].

Savenkova L.B., Galiy A.S. made an attempt to identify the type of boss in the current linguistic culture, namely in social networks. In their opinion, the boss is an individual who enters into direct official business contact with the author of the speech. Based on the re-

sults of the study, the authors make the following conclusion that there are two images or two sides of the linguo-communicative type "boss". First: "The chief as an ideal (model personality) is characterized by the ability not only to organize the work of subordinates and to fulfill the task that is set for the labor association. This is an objective person, combining a position and informal leadership, sociable, responsive to the needs of subordinates, capable of cooperation."

The second image: "The boss as a reality rarely meets the ideal. More often, this is a person who seeks to acquire a relatively high social status (the boss appears as an individual who is subordinate to a completely observable circle of subordinates) and the benefits associated with it. The chief, for the most part, is not endowed with high intelligence, does not know how to objectively assess the situation and organize the labor process, exploits his subordinates, is distinguished by aggressiveness, and is capable of psychological violence. In addition to this, he is quite ambitious and approaches his person, overestimating self-esteem" [6, 95].

Of course, the relationship between the leader and subordinates, starting from the moment they are hired, relationships in the process of work and dismissal, is one of the important points in the field of business communication. In this regard, we are interested in the problem of the functions of speech behavior implemented in the conditions of official communication, limited by the social role and status of communicants.

The material of the study was examples from the literary works of Gorbatoev B., Sanbaev S., Arkhipenko V., Ustinova T. and others. The research methods were discourse analysis of the text, as well as methods of semantic, syntactic, contextual analysis.

By regulating and controlling the activities of subordinates, managers enter into interaction with them, which in form and content differs both from ordinary interpersonal communication and from that which is typical for communication of professionals of the same status. The interaction of the subjects of the organization at the level of hierarchical positions and activity roles, to which this or that conventional communicative behavior is assigned, can be called hierarchical. Within the framework of this interaction, the subject of the organization acts, first of all, as a hierarchical person whose behavior depends on his position on the career ladder.

Description of the spatial characteristics of the premises, symbolic things that demonstrate the social status of the communicant, actualize one of the most important functions of speech behavior. The socially-oriented function on the part of the superior is manifested in the fact that it actualizes a special non-verbal behavior that demonstrates his social status, his actions are authoritarian and testify to his high position. Even an office, furniture - all this is designed to show its significance.

"But, having become the district Komsomol leader, he ceased to be our Alyosha. Is it really that simple, thin, restless boy from the factory street, whom I loved so much in childhood? Where did these important, rounded gestures come from? This imperious,

sharp, demanding tone, and this look, empty cold, not noticing anyone, a look that passes through a person, coloring and not lighting up? I was overwhelmed by his noisiness. Everywhere - in the theater, on the street, in the club - he walked, pushing people aside and talking loudly. He couldn't speak quietly. He did not know how to listen - he was used to being listened to. He did not know how to agree - he was used to agreeing with him, obeying him. And everything he said, explained, told, did - he did noisily, sweepingly, in a businesslike way" [7, 6].

Social distance is also preserved when expressing verbal behavior that emphasizes the position of the subordinate in relation to the superior, which is manifested by a dismissive attitude towards a person with a low status. The upbringing learned in the "superior" group allows the representative of the group to feel at the height of his position in any case, emphasizing his high status in front of his subordinates: *"Welcomingly and majestically smiling, she said that she was glad and happy to see guests at her place, and apologized that she and her husband were deprived this time of the opportunity to invite the gentlemen of the officers to spend the night with them. From her beautiful majestic smile, which instantly disappeared from her face every time she turned away from the guests for something, it was clear that in her lifetime she had seen many mister officers, that she was not up to them now, and if she invited them to her house and apologizes, it is only because her upbringing and position in the world require it" [8].*

Such awareness of one's group belonging to one of the groups "superior" - "lower" is manifested in the following social distance and regulation of social relations between the privileged classes and those groups that occupy lower positions in the system of social inequality: *"he [Franklin - T.K.] understood that no reconciliation with the lords of the English king is possible, either now or in the future. For seventeen whole years he was a guest in the homes of these important gentlemen, they kindly conversed with him, paying tribute to his learning, his inquisitiveness, his philosophy: and now they, grinning, listened to how this horloder attorney abused him, how he showered him with street scolding. Now they have shown themselves. Now it became clear how happy they were to humiliate him. They humiliated him because he was no match for them. Because he is not a noble. And a simple tradesman, the son of a soap maker, who dared to open his mouth in defense of little people [9, 81].*

The position of social orientation is also visible in relation to junior military ranks in relation to the highest: *"Malykhin was the first to slide down the ladder, followed by Kraukhov just as quickly. Printing a step, they approached the officer, clicked their heels in unison, and froze with protruding chins" [10, 43].*

The subordinate understands his place and his position on the bottom rung of the social ladder: *"Perhaps you will seat him next to you, venerable khan! he remarked with ill-concealed anger. Askar shook his head: - Khan's dastarkhan is not for me. If you'll excuse me, khan, we'll go where it's easier" [11, 147].*

The attitude towards the subordinates from the superiors may be dismissive, for example: "*The secretary tried to figure out the reason, but Yevgeny Petrovich looked at her the way the dean of the faculty of international relations once looked at him. The secretary immediately shut up and went away*" [12, 222].

Thus, the analysis of the actualization of signs of social symbolization in a non-verbal form shows that they perform regulative and socially oriented functions, helping to maintain social distance in a situation of status inequality.

Hierarchical communication is the interaction of the subjects of the organization at the level of hierarchical positions and activity roles, which are assigned to one or another conventional communicative behavior. The verbal markers of hierarchical communication are intentional and non-intentional, direct and indirect forms of speech influence - categorical and non-categorical directives: orders, instructions, prohibitions from superiors and requests, wishes, advice and recommendations from lower subjects of communication.

At the same time, in the "higher-lower" status dichotomy, the range of verbal means used by the boss is much wider than those used by subordinates, since social norms allow greater freedom of communicative behavior of the subject occupying a higher position on the career ladder [13, 26].

Signs of social symbolization in a non-verbal form perform regulative and socially-oriented functions, helping to maintain social distance in a situation of status inequality.

An analysis of the functions implemented in a situation of symbolic interactionism shows that, in addition to the instrumental and regulatory functions, within the "we-them" groups, a socially oriented function is observed, when the lower ones orient themselves in relation to the higher ones, and the higher ones tend to keep a distance in relation to those standing on the lower level. rungs of the social ladder.

Thus, verbal and non-verbal symbolic signs - tools of social regulation, used in the realized meaning, perform the function of regulating social relations and the function of social orientation, when communicants use the language in accordance with their position in society.

References

1. Folomeeva T.V., Fedotova S.V. The phenomenon of social status in modern Russian society //Psychological research. 2016. V. 9, No. 48. P. 7. <http://psystudy.ru/index.php/num/2016v9n48/1309-folomeeva48.html>
2. Shibutani T. Social psychology: Per. from English. M., 1969.
3. Badretdinov Z.A. // Bulletin of the Chelyabinsk State University. - 2008. - No. 11. - P.38-47
4. Schutz A. The semantic structure of the world A. Schutz M.// Selected: The world glowing with meaning. - M., 2004. - P.742
5. Dubinina I.I. Ways of expressing hierarchical relationships in organizational communication. Abstract Diss. competition uch. Art. Ph.D. Volgograd, 2007 - 219 p. URI: <https://dspace.kpfu.ru/xmlui/handle/net/154068>
6. Savenkova L.B., Galiy A.S. Syntagmatic connections of the word boss as a means of verbal embodiment of the linguo-communicative type of the same name in social media//Scientific thought of Caucasus 2022, No. 6, p. -kak-sredstvo-verbalnogo-voploscheniya-odnoimennogo-lingvokommunikativnogo-tipazha-v-sotsialnyh-media.pdf
7. Gorbatov B. Alexey Gaidash. Sobr. op. in 4 volumes. Volume 2. - M.: Pravda, 1988. - p. 5-266
8. Chekhov A.P. Kiss // Chekhov A.P. Complete works and letters: In 30 volumes. Works: In 18 volumes / Academy of Sciences of the USSR. Institute of world literature. them. A. M. Gorky. - M.: Nauka, 1974-1982. T. 6. [Stories]. - M. Nauka, 1976. - S. 406-423. <http://chehovlit.ru/chehov/text/poceluj.htm>
9. Feuchtwanger L. Foxes in the vineyard. - M.: Publishing house AST. Harvest, 2014
10. Archipenko V. Look for a connection. - M.: Young Guard, 1977
11. Sanbaev S. When they crave a myth: Tales and stories. - Alma-Ata: Zhazushi, 1989. - 348s.
12. Ustinova T. Big evil and small dirty tricks. - M.: EKSMO, 2009. - 352 p.
13. Authority and communication (collective monograph). Aspects of language and communication series. Issue 4. - Voronezh: Voronezh State University; Aleinikovs Publishing House, 2008. - 216 p. <http://tpl1999.narod.ru/index/0-70>